

Effect of Quality Practices on Customer Satisfaction and Its Impact on Business Performance of Small Medium Enterprise in Banda Aceh, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of implementing total quality management on customer satisfaction and the business performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the city of Banda Aceh, Indonesia. The research sample of 100 business owners was taken by purposive sampling. Data collection using a questionnaire and then the data were analyzed using simple linear regression statistical tools that are operationalized with AMOS. The study found that quality practice had a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction and business performance of SMEs. Customer satisfaction mediates the effect of quality practice on business performance.

Keywords: Business Performance, Customer Satisfaction, Quality Practice and Structural Equation Model

I. INTRODUCTION

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have an important role in driving the economic growth of a region (Amri, 2017). Moreover, these businesses are generally occupied by small and medium entrepreneurs, including the home industry. The development of SMEs affects a number of variables such as employment opportunities (Amri, 2018; Muliadi & Amri, 2019), exports (Amri, & Aimon, 2017; Amri & Nazamuddin, 2018a) economic growth and income inequality (Amri & Nazamuddin, 2018b) and other macroeconomic variables in a country's economy (Maulana & Iskandar, 2018). In the end, the development of SMEs has an impact on national economic improvement.

Along with the economic development of the city of Banda Aceh, the existence of SMEs also showed significant development. One of the business groups is a furniture business or furniture business. Until now the business is spread in almost all corners of the city of Banda Aceh. The existence of these businesses certainly can not be separated from the demands of the community's needs for the products produced. The business performance of the business certainly cannot be separated from the ability of the owner/manager of the business in satisfying the needs of its consumers. Responding to these needs, they strive to implement total quality management to improve production quality.

Implementation of quality practices in the furniture business, among others, is manifested in the form of selecting quality wood raw materials, the use of skilled workers so that they can produce products following the wishes of consumers and so forth. Every furniture business in the city of Banda Aceh has tried to provide the best for its consumers. But in reality, the business performance of these businesses is relatively different from each other.

Theoretically and empirically, business performance can be influenced by customer satisfaction and the implementation of quality practices. As the research findings of Nilssona et al. (2001) concluded that the implementation of quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction and business results. Consistent with these findings, research conducted by ul Hassan et al (2012) for the case of Pakistan's manufacturing industry also found that business performance was significantly influenced by customer satisfaction and quality practices.

The manager of SMEs in the city of Banda Aceh has also tried to implement quality practices oriented to improving the quality of the products produced. Therefore, the question is whether customer satisfaction and business results in the business are related to the company's quality practices. This study aims to determine the effect of quality practice on customer satisfaction and business performance of SMEs in Banda Aceh City, Indonesia. In contrast to

previous studies, this study not only places customer satisfaction as a predictor variable for business performance but also as an intervening variable between quality practice and business performance of SMEs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Business Performance

Business performance can be interpreted as the results obtained from business activity. Achievement of business performance is inseparable from the ability of the business to meet the needs of its customers, so performance can also be defined as the extent to which an operation meets performance objectives and the main steps to meet customer needs. Performance measurement is very important for a business organization to achieve optimal business performance (Demirbag et al. 2006). Zehir and Esin (2009) states that the measurement of business performance can be done through 2 dimensions: innovation performance and employee performance

2.2 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the feeling of the customer after buying the goods or services (Kotler, 2010: 46). Customer expectations are shaped based on their experiences, friends' suggestions and advertisements delivered by service companies. Customers choose to provide services based on this expectation and after enjoying the service they will compare it with what they expect. If the service they enjoy turns out to be far below what they expect, it results in dissatisfaction (Farnita & Amri, 2013).

2.3 Quality Practices

Quality is the totality of the shape and characteristics of goods or services that show the ability to satisfy needs that are clearly or hidden (Render and Heizer, 2004). These needs are then further defined by several user-oriented and product-oriented researchers. Krajewski and Ritzman (2006) state that customers define quality in a variety of ways, namely: (1) conformance to specifications or compliance with expected specifications; (2) value or price; (3) fitness of use or according to its use, reliability or service, service or service; (4) support or service support; (5) psychological impressions or images, for example beauty, cleanliness.

Referring to some of these definitions it can be concluded that: (1) quality includes products, services, people, processes and the environment, that is, things that are produced by companies and accepted by consumers and society, (2) quality is a measure determined by consumers. The measure is then translated into technical specifications that can meet the desires of the consumer, (3) quality is dynamic, so changes must be dynamic also in the effort to fulfill the quality.

2.4 The link between quality practices and customer satisfaction

Quality has become an important aspect of competition in the global market. Every company can improve its performance through continuous improvement in business activities that are focused on consumers, which include the entire organization and an emphasis on flexibility and quality. Therefore, quality and management are always associated with continuous improvement activities to win the competition (Krajewski and Ritzman, 2006). In the practice of quality in companies known as the term total quality management (TQM), is an approach that should be done by today's organizations to improve the quality of its products, reduce production costs and increase productivity. TQM implementation also has a positive impact on production costs and on revenue (Gaspersz, 2005). Other evidence also shows that companies that pursue TQM best practices can achieve higher profits and cashflows as well as greater shareholder value (Corbett and Rastrick, 2000).

The relationship between quality practice and business results is also stated in the research findings of Truong et al. (2014) which concluded that quality management practices are directly related directly and indirectly to the company's operational performance. Research conducted by Ahmad & Schroeder (2003) also found that quality practices affect the company's operational performance. The better the quality practice, the better the operational performance. Likewise, the results of Prajogo & Sohal's (2003) research also prove a positive relationship between the two variables. Furthermore, ul Hassan et al's (2012) study of 171 managers of Pakistan's manufacturing industry also concluded that quality practice positively impacts business performance. Likewise, the study of Jaafreh & Al-Abedallat (2013) supports several previous research findings that quality practice influences business performance.

Based on the explanation above, the first hypothesis is that stated as follows:

H₁: The quality practices has a positive effect on customer satisfaction

2.5 The link between quality practices and business performance

Since the early 1980s, TQM has received the most attention from managers, because it has proven capable of improving company performance. Total Quality Management (TQM) is a new paradigm in running a business that seeks to maximize organizational competitiveness through a focus on customer satisfaction, the involvement of all employees, and continuous improvement in the quality of products, services, people, processes and organizational environment (Krajewski and Ritzman, 2006). Efforts to increase customer satisfaction can be done through the implementation of quality practices for goods and services produced (Terziovski, 2006). This is because in general consumers want good quality goods and services..

The existence of the effect of quality practice on customer satisfaction has been proven by several researchers (Terziovski, 2006; Su et al., 2008). Empirical research conducted by Ooi et al. (2011) in several manufacturing companies in Malaysia proved that quality practice can improve customer satisfaction. This finding is supported by the results of Anil & Satish's research (2017) which also proves the existence of quality practices towards customer satisfaction.

Referring to the description of a number of empirical studies as explained above, the second hypothesis as follows:

H₂: The quality practice has a positive effect on business performance

2.6 The link between customer satisfaction and business performance

Customer satisfaction can have a positive impact on business performance. This is due, business results such as sales or business profits derived from certain business activities that come from purchases made by customers. The higher the satisfaction they feel, the higher their willingness to make purchases so that the company's business performance also increases. Conversely, if customers feel dissatisfied with the goods and services they obtain from a company, they will tend to look for goods and services from other companies. In the end, the company is not able to satisfy its customers, then it's business performance will decline..

The relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance is proven by Nilsson et al. (2001) that customer satisfaction can improve business performance. The results of an empirical study conducted by Williams & Naumann (2011) also prove a positive relationship between the two variables. The higher the customer satisfaction the higher the business performance (Azigwe et al., 2016; Eklof et al., 2018). Conversely, when customer satisfaction declines, then these conditions negatively impact business performance (Leo et al., 2009; Kanten & Darma, 2017).

Referring to the description of empirical studies as explained above, the third hypothesis as follows:

H₃: The customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on business performance

III. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

This study operationalized four variables consisting of business performance, customer satisfaction and quality practices. The business performance and customer satisfaction are endogenous variables. While, quality practice is exogenous variables. The relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables is not only supported by theoretical basics but also recommended by most studies as explained previously. Therefore, the research framework of this study as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1
Research Framework

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at SMEs in the City of Banda Aceh. The population in this study was all SMEs. The research sample is limited to only 100 business owners who were taken by purposive sampling with the provisions of the business has been operating for more than three years. Questionnaires containing closed questions were used as data collection instruments. The questionnaire contained several statements relating to business performance, customer satisfaction, and quality practices. Each statement is given five choices of answers in the form of the agreement including strongly agree, agree, disagree, disagree and strongly disagree (Amri & Surya, 2013; Iskandar & Amri, 2013; Amri, 2014; Amri, 2015; Amri & Marwiyati, 2019). Each alternative answer choices are given a score based on a Likert 1-5 scale. Respondents were asked to determine choices for their answers to each of the related statements (Ratnawati & Amri, 2013; Amri et al., 2018). Following the objectives of the study, it can be explained that customer satisfaction is a function of quality practice. Furthermore, business performance is a function of customer satisfaction and quality practice. So that the existence of customer satisfaction is positioned as a mediating variable between quality practices and business performance. The analytical model used is the structural equation model (SEM) with AMOS 21.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 The result of confirmatory factor analysis test and measurement model

In this study, the variables or constructs studied consisted of business performance, customer satisfaction, and quality practices. The confirmatory factors analysis is intended to test whether the indicators used to measure each variable can manifest the measured variable. In other words, this CFA analysis is also useful for determining whether a measurement indicator used to measure variables is declared valid or not.

Statistically, an indicator can be expressed as a manifestation of the measured variable if it has a loading factor value > 0.70, a critical ratio (CR) value > 2.00 and a p-value < 0.05 (Ghozali, 2011). When an indicator does not meet these criteria, the indicator is reduced from the model and then the CFA test is continued at a later stage until all the indicators or manifest variables meet the specified criteria.

Table 1. The result of confirmatory factor analysis

	<i>Loading Factor</i>	<i>Critical Ratio</i>	<i>p-value</i>
QP1 <--- Quality_Practices	.771		
QP2 <--- Quality_Practices	.740	8.463	***
QP3 <--- Quality_Practices	.713	8.130	***
QP4 <--- Quality_Practices	.798	9.164	***
QP5 <--- Quality_Practices	.719	8.209	***
CS5 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.804		
CS4 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.795	9.910	***
CS3 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.795	9.917	***
CS2 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.806	10.079	***
CS1 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.710	8.627	***
BP5 <--- Business_Performance	.804		
BP4 <--- Business_Performance	.819	10.549	***
BP3 <--- Business_Performance	.825	10.649	***
BP2 <--- Business_Performance	.766	9.676	***
BP1 <--- Business_Performance	.841	10.916	***

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

Based on Table 2 above, it can be seen that all the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) testing criteria have been fulfilled, where all indicators have a loading factor value above 0.70, a critical ratio (CR) value above 2.00 and a p-value below 0.05. This means that the indicators for each variable as shown in the above are indicators that can confirm the variable under study.

Following the framework of the research concept, endogenous variables in this study consisted of two variables including customer satisfaction and business performance. Furthermore, quality practices are the exogenous variable. Measures of goodness of fit in the SEM use several measurements consisting of X2 or chi-square statistics, GFI

(Goodness of Fit Index), AGI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) TLI (Tucker Lewis Index) and CFI (Comparative Fit Index)). Measurement model test results as shown in table 2.

Table 2. The result of measurement model

Goodness-of-Fit Index	Value Criterion	Result of test	Evaluasi Model
χ^2 - Chi-square	$X^2_{hit} < X^2_{tab}$	94,440 < 215.563	Good
Significance Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,091	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,931	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,924	Good
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,976	Good
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,969	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,067	Good
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	0,661	Good

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

Based on Table 2 above, it can be seen that the X^2 test is 94.440. While the X^2 table of 215.563 is greater when compared to the X^2 test. In other words, the value of X^2 test < X^2 table (94.440 < 215.563). This means that the X^2 test statistically meets the specified criteria, so the model is declared not good. The probability value or p-value of the measurement model in this second stage of 0.091 also meets the specified criteria above 0.05. This means that judging from the p-value, the measurement model results meet the provisions of the goodness of fit index.

Furthermore, based on the criteria the GFI value has also fulfilled the requirements which are equal to 0.931 greater than the required value of 0.90. Likewise, the AGFI of 0.924 is also greater than 0.90. The TLI and CFA also meet the requirements, namely 0.976 and 0.969, respectively. Then the RMSEA of 0.067 (<0.08) also meets the requirements of the goodness of fit index. Therefore, the measurement model shows that all criteria have been met. Thus, the next step can be continued to the full structural model to test the causality relationship between variables following the research paradigm that was made previously.

After the measurement test, the model is analyzed through confirmatory factor analysis and it is seen that each indicator can be used to define a latent construct, then the next step in using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) as a data analysis tool is to conduct a structural test of the entire model. In this case, the researcher directly tests the relationship between all variables (constructs) studied by involving all the indicators on each construct. The results of the full structural model that explains the interrelationships among all research variables are shown in Figure 2.

Furthermore, the results of the full structural model explain the relationship between the research variables as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
The result of Full Structural Model

Figure 2 above not only shows the estimated coefficient values of each exogenous variable against endogenous variables but also shows the loading factor value of each indicator (manifest variable) against these variables. The estimated coefficient of quality practices on customer satisfaction and business performance as shown in table 3.

Table 3. Path coefficients of each research variable

			Estimate Coefficient	C.R.	P-Value	Hypothesis
Customer_Satisfaction	<---	Quality_Practices	.348	3.385	***	Accepted
Business_Performance	<---	Quality_Practices	.394	3.832	***	Accepted
Business_Performance	<---	Customer_Satisfaction	.179	2.274	.021	Accepted

Source : Primary Data (Processed), 2019

*** denotes for the significant at 99% level.

From the table 3 above can be understood that quality practice has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and business performance. Likewise, the influence of customer satisfaction on business performance is also positive and significant. So that the existence of customer satisfaction can be positioned as a mediating variable between quality practice on the one hand and business performance on the other. Based on the table above, the discussion of the influence between variables as represented in the following section.

5.2 Analysis of the effect of quality practices on customer satisfaction

The implementation of quality practices in a company has a positive and significant impact on business performance. This is statistically shown by the estimated coefficient of 0.348 and the p-value of 0.001 (<0.05). The better the quality practice, the better business performance. Conversely, when companies do not apply the quality practice, these conditions have an impact on decreasing the business performance of SMEs. Thus the first hypothesis (H1) which states that Quality practice has a positive and significant effect on business performance can be accepted.

The existence of a positive and significant effect of quality practice on the business performance of SMEs, confirms the results of Truong et al. (2014) which concluded that quality management practices are directly related directly and indirectly to the company's operational performance. Research conducted by Ahmad & Schroeder (2003) also found that quality practices affect the company's operational performance. This finding is in line with the results of an empirical study conducted by Ahmad & Schroeder (2003) also found that quality practices affect the company's operational performance. The better the quality practice, the better the operational performance. Likewise, the results of Prajogo & Sohal's (2003) research also prove a positive relationship between the two variables.

5.3 Analysis of the effect of quality practices on business performance

The quality practice has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction with an estimated coefficient of 0.394 and a p-value of 0.001 (<0.05). This means the better the quality practice the higher the customer satisfaction. In general, customers want good quality products and can meet their needs. The application of quality practices in SMEs can improve the quality of the products produced. For example, efforts to improve the quality of raw materials for production have an impact on improving the quality and durability of goods produced and in turn can provide satisfaction for consumers. Conversely, when companies ignore the quality of raw materials, then these conditions harm the quality of production and in turn, are unable to meet consumer needs. This has led to a significant influence on quality practice on customer satisfaction. Based on the description, the second (H2) stating Quality practice has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction is accepted.

The findings of this study confirm the results of empirical research conducted by Terziovski (2006) and Su et al. (2008) who also found that influential quality practice can encourage increased customer satisfaction. The argument underlying the significance of this influence is that consumers generally expect that their needs can be met with good quality products. The results of an empirical study conducted by Ooi et al. (2011) in several manufacturing companies in Malaysia proved that quality practice can improve customer satisfaction.

5.4 Analysis of the effect of customer satisfaction on business performance

Customer satisfaction can have a positive impact on business performance, indicated by an estimated coefficient of 0.179 and a p-value of 0.021 (<0.05). Consumers who are satisfied with the products they consume will try to make a repeat purchase. As a result, the level of company sales has increased. Conversely, a decrease in customer satisfaction adversely affects consumer loyalty. They will even try to leave the product and look for other products that can meet their needs. These conditions harm company sales. This is what causes a positive and significant effect on customer

satisfaction on business performance. Thus the third hypothesis (H3) which states customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on business performance can be accepted.

The significant effect of customer satisfaction on business performance supports the results of research by Nilsson et al. (2001) that customer satisfaction can improve business performance. This finding is also in line with the results of a study by Williams & Naumann (2011) which also revealed a positive relationship between the two variables. The higher the customer satisfaction the higher the business performance (Azigwe et al., 2016; Eklof et al., 2018).

Furthermore, testing the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the causality relationship between practice quality and business performance refers to the opinion Referring to the opinion of Baron and Kenny (1986). The test results indicate that the direct effect of quality practices on business performance is significant. Furthermore, the indirect effect of quality practices on business performance through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable is also significant. Thus, the mediating effect that is raised by consumer satisfaction is partial mediation. This finding is consistent with the results of the study of Nilsson et al. (2001) which concluded that the implementation of quality practices has a significant effect on customer satisfaction and business performance, and customer satisfaction mediates the effect of quality practices on business performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The quality practice has a positive and significant effect on business results. The better the quality practice at SMEs, the better the business results of the business, whether in the form of sales, profits, use of raw materials or use of labor. The quality practice has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The better the quality practice the higher the customer satisfaction for the products produced. Referring to the conclusions described above, the suggestions and recommendations of this study are as follows.

1. The owners and managers of SMEs in the city of Banda Aceh need to improve quality practices in the companies they manage. Operationally, efforts to improve quality practice can be done by increasing the ability of employees to work, providing quality raw materials and implementing production planning oriented to improving the quality of output.
2. The owners and managers of SMEs in the city of Banda Aceh need to increase customer satisfaction. Operationally, efforts to improve customer satisfaction can be done by improving the quality of the products produced, providing product delivery services to the customer's place, and other efforts that can improve customer satisfaction.

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